

Dermofat Graft as a Dual Solution: Lip Revision and Cleft Rhinoplasty in Secondary Cleft Surgery

Michele Yoselin¹, Putu Trisna Utami²

¹Intern Doctor, Department of Plastic Reconstructive and Aesthetic Surgery, Bali Mandara Regional Public Hospital, Denpasar, Bali, Indonesia

²Craniomaxillofacial Surgeon, Department of Plastic Reconstructive and Aesthetic Surgery, Bali Mandara Regional Public Hospital, Denpasar, Bali, Indonesia

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Cleft lip and palate remain among the most common congenital craniofacial anomalies. Secondary deformities frequently require additional surgery due to scarring, asymmetry, and cartilage deficiency. Dermofat grafting has re-emerged as a promising reconstructive option, offering stable volume, natural contour, and lower donor-site morbidity compared to traditional grafts or implants.

Case Illustration: An 8-year-old girl with a history of bilateral cleft lip repair and alveolar bone grafting presented with lip asymmetry, vermilion retraction, coloboma, and nasal deformity, resulting in aesthetic concerns and psychosocial impact. The patient underwent single-stage secondary lip revision and cleft rhinoplasty. Lip revision followed Mulliken's technique with scar and coloboma excision, orbicularis oris release and reorientation, and white-roll augmentation using a dermofat graft harvested from the gluteal fold. Cleft rhinoplasty was performed using Tajima's reverse-U incision, with repositioning of the lower lateral cartilages, and dermofat graft placement along the dorsum and tip.

Discussion: Dermofat grafting provided durable soft-tissue volume and enhanced contour, addressing vermilion asymmetry, white-roll deficiency, and nasal projection. This single-stage approach reduced donor-site morbidity, minimized the need for staged procedures, and offered psychosocial benefits by improving facial aesthetics during critical developmental stages.

Conclusions: Dermofat grafting is a safe, versatile, and cost-effective autologous option for secondary cleft lip and nasal reconstruction. It represents a practical strategy in resource-limited settings, while offering both aesthetic and psychosocial outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Dermofat Graft, Lip Revision, Cleft Rhinoplasty, Secondary Cleft Surgery, Cleft Lip Palate

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INTRODUCTION

Cleft lip and palate are still one of the most frequent congenital craniofacial abnormalities globally, and its worldwide incidence varies from 1/700 to 1/1000 live births.¹ Although there has been development in primary surgical strategy, secondary deformities are still the main challenge.² Secondary abnormalities after lip and palate repair lead to poor aesthetic appearance, but also psychosocial as well as functional impairment among patients. Such deformities can present with lip asymmetry, vermilion notching, coloboma, hypertrophic scarring and nasal deformities that often require

further surgery for functional outcomes as well as psychosocial health.^{3,4}

There remain many early traditional methods of reconstruction, including local flaps, cartilage grafts and even alloplastic implants which are still in use today but have associated limitations such as morbidity at the donor site, risk of infection and long term reabsorption.⁵ Autologous fat grafting has gained traction over the past few years with respect to contour restoration, but the ability to achieve sustained results is often limited by unpredictable resorption and frequent requirement of additional procedure. These are precisely the implications of dermofat grafts, consisting of

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dermis and subcutaneous fat in its structure which make them attractive autologous material for use in reconstructive and aesthetic surgery due to lower donor site morbidity associated with harvesting the same from the donor sites and a high degree of biocompatibility.⁶

Dermofat grafting has re-emerged as a promising alternative that combines the benefits of fat volume with dermal support, reducing resorption and providing long-lasting results.⁷ Its application in cleft lip and rhinoplasty reconstruction has been increasingly reported in recent years.⁸ Recent literature has expanded their indications from their traditional contour improvement role to include more complex reconstructive facial surgery like skull base reconstruction, cleft rhinoplasty, and cleft lip/palate deformity correction, with safety as well as aesthetic reliability proven in these applications.⁹

Most articles in cleft operations are devoted to their use for lip augmentation, but their use in the simultaneous repair of lip and nasal deformities is poorly documented. As cleft rhinoplasty is often complicated by cartilage shortage and scarring, dermofat grafts can be a reliable option in volume replacement and soft-tissue augmentation. This case is important to report because it demonstrates how dermofat grafts can be an alternative solution for secondary cleft lip repair as lip and nasal deformities can be treated in a single surgery. This approach may decrease the need for staged surgery, optimize aesthetic outcomes, and provide new insights for expanding the role of dermofat grafts in cleft surgery.

CASE ILLUSTRATION

An 8-year-old girl came to Bali Mandara General Hospital with complaints of lip asymmetry, nasal deformity, and prominent surgical scars. The patient had a history of bilateral cleft lip and alveolar surgery including primary labioplasty in 2017 followed by an alveolar bone graft in 2024. Even after primary surgery, there are still abnormalities that cause significant aesthetic disturbances and the risk of loss of self-confidence in children as they grow older. The patient was in good general condition with no functional complaints such as pain, feeding difficulty, or airway infection.

Physical examination revealed complicated deformities of the nose and lip. Bilateral post-labioplasty coloboma of the lip was observed along with shortened philtrum. The white skin roll appeared disrupted due to scarring, resulting in poorly defined lip contour. The Cupid's bow was poorly defined with a residual coloboma at its tip, while the wet vermilion and mucosa were retracted superiorly. Nasal inspection disclosed severe nasal deformity. The lower lateral cartilage (LLC) was displaced superiorly, with the nose tip being underdeveloped. The columella was short, and the nasal floor appeared widened, creating an asymmetric and disproportionate nasal contour. The surgical

plan consisted of secondary lip revision combined with cleft rhinoplasty using dermofat grafting.

On the Asher–McDade scale, the patient was scored 4 (poor appearance) for nasal form due to an underdeveloped nasal tip, 4 (poor appearance) for nasal symmetry because of columellar deviation and alar asymmetry, 5 (very poor appearance) for vermilion border reflecting severe disruption of the white roll and colobomas, and 4 for nasal profile with noticeable flattening (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Preoperative assessment of nasal form, nasal symmetry, and vermilion border based on the Asher–McDade scale.

The patient was prepared to undergo surgical correction secondary to lip revision and cleft rhinoplasty post bilateral cleft lip and palate surgery. The patient and family received counseling on the surgical technique, the application of autologous tissue, and the structured postoperative care protocol aimed at optimizing functional and aesthetic outcomes. Postoperative instructions included wound management, nasal stent care, early mobilization, and maintenance of general hygiene. The patient was systemically fit (ASA I) and underwent general anesthesia via orotracheal intubation. The patient was positioned in head ring supine position. The surgery was started after a clean and sterile face and left gluteal area, which served as the donor site were achieved. Two procedures were performed are lip revision with dermofat grafting and cleft rhinoplasty with dermofat grafting.

Fig. 2. Intraoperative overview: (a) incision design, (b-c) dermis-fat graft harvest, and (d) nasal dorsum graft insertion.

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For the lip revision, an incision was made following Mulliken's technique (Figure 2a). Hypertrophic scar tissue and residual coloboma were excised. Intraoperative assessment revealed intact orbicularis oris fibers tethered to the piriform base. The adhesions were released and the muscle rotated into the lip. A lateral flap was elevated, and subperiosteal dissection of lateral maxillary buttress and piriform rim was performed followed by medial approximation. The nasal base was secured to the muscle and layered closure was performed. White roll of the skin was reconstructed with a gluteal fold fat graft.

For the cleft rhinoplasty, a skin incision was made using Tajima's reverse U technique, followed by subcutaneous dissection extending to the nasal dorsum and alar regions. The lower lateral cartilages (LCC) were repositioned and secured with absorbable monofilament sutures. To correct nasal tip and dorsum defects, a dermofat graft harvested from the left gluteal fold (Figure 2b) was contoured and placed along the nasal dorsum (Figure 2c), then fixed to the surrounding tissues with absorbable monofilament sutures to ensure stability and symmetry. Layered closure was then performed. Following secondary lip revision and cleft rhinoplasty with dermofat grafting, the patient's scores improved to 2 (good appearance) for nasal form with better-defined tip projection, 2 (good appearance) for nasal symmetry with improved columellar alignment, and 2 (good appearance) for vermilion border reflecting restoration of white roll continuity (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. Postoperative result showing improved nasal form, nasal symmetry, and vermilion border (Asher–McDade score: 2 for all parameters).

Evaluation at day 11 after reconstruction (Figure 4b-5b) showed notable improvement in lip and nasal contour. The white skin roll appeared more continuous, the Cupid's bow was better defined, and the vermilion height was more balanced with reduced retraction of the mucosa. Early edema was still present but did not obscure the overall correction. The nasal tip projection improved, with the columella lengthened and the lower lateral cartilage repositioned to achieve a more symmetric nasal base. One month after reconstruction (Figure 4c-5c) demonstrated further refinement of the surgical outcome. Edema had largely resolved, allowing clearer visualization of the reconstructed contours. At the 60-day follow-up (Figure 4d-5d), the surgical outcome demonstrated stable healing with no signs

of infection, graft loss, or scar contracture. Lip contour remained symmetric with preserved vermilion height and natural curvature of the Cupid's bow. The white roll remained continuous and smooth, with no palpable irregularities or step-offs along the mucocutaneous junction. The grafted volume was well maintained, with no clinically appreciable resorption. The nasal also remained stable, showing sustained projection of the nasal tip and improved definition of the alar contour. The columella retained its lengthening effect, contributing to a more balanced nasal-labial angle and improved nasal profile. Symmetry between the left and right alar bases was preserved, with a more natural and proportional appearance compared with earlier postoperative stages.

Fig. 4. Anterior view, Day 1 (a), Day 11 (b), Day 32 (c), Day 60 (d) Follow-up

Fig. 5. Worm's eye view, Day 1 (a), Day 11 (b), Day 32 (c), Day 60 (d) Follow-up

Comparison using the Asher–McDade scale demonstrated notable improvement from preoperative to postoperative assessment. Initially, the patient presented with poor nasal form, asymmetry, and discontinuity of the vermilion border, each scoring 4 (poor appearance). At the latest follow-up, all parameters improved to a score of 2 (good appearance), reflecting enhanced nasal tip projection,

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improved columellar alignment, and restoration of the white roll and vermilion contour (Figure 6).

Fig. 6. Asher–McDade score comparison showing improvement from: (a) 4 (poor appearance) to (b) 2 (good appearance) in nasal form, nasal symmetry, and vermilion border.

Functionally, the patient reported normal oral competence, no speech difficulty, and no discomfort during smiling or lip movement. Psychosocially, the patient and family expressed increased confidence and satisfaction with the outcome. Overall, the 60-day evaluation demonstrated durable improvements in both structural and aesthetic components of the lip and nasal complex, with results consistent with favorable graft integration and stable correction.

DISCUSSION

Secondary deformities after cleft lip repair remain a significant challenge due to scar tissue, asymmetry, and cartilage deficiency, often necessitating staged procedures for satisfactory outcomes.^{3,10} In the present case, the patient demonstrated bilateral lip colobomas, disrupted white-roll definition, vermilion retraction, and nasal deformities with lower displaced lateral cartilage and an underdeveloped tip. Correcting such complex problems required a reconstructive modality that could restore contour, provide durable volume, and minimize morbidity. Dermofat grafting has emerged as a valuable tool in this context. Compared to isolated fat grafts with a potential for variable resorption, dermofat grafts are related to long-standing contour stability owing to the dermal scaffold-induced survival of adipocytes.⁵

Clinical studies and systematic reviews confirm improved outcomes with dermofat compared to fat grafts alone, particularly in scar tissue where the insufficiency of soft tissues is more pronounced.^{4,6} In lip reconstruction, dermofat improves vermilion projection and white-roll definition and has higher patient satisfaction and less resorption than fat grafting.⁴ Similarly, dermofat grafts offer reliable augmentation in nasal reconstruction. They provide dorsal and tip support without leading to synthetic implant-related complications such as extrusion or infection.^{11,12} Case reports have also shown successful dermofat use in cleft rhinoplasty with stable outcomes and reduced donor-site morbidity. Comparison studies suggest that dermofat achieves better soft-tissue shape with fewer donor-site complications than bone grafts, while the latter may still be useful for providing rigid structural support.⁷

The uniqueness of the present case lies in the simultaneous use of dermofat grafts on the nose and lip in a single procedure. The technique minimized the need for staged reconstruction, reduced donor-site morbidity, and allowed for the simultaneous complete correction of colobomas, vermilion asymmetry, and nasal tip deficiency. This follows increasing evidence of the value of dermofat as a multipurpose, autologous graft for secondary cleft reconstruction.^{10,12} Along with anatomical correction, secondary cleft deformities have a psychosocial effect as well. Even in the absence of functional impairment, children experience low self-esteem, peer rejection, and decreased social confidence due to visible scars and asymmetry.¹³ Aesthetic issues brought forward by our patient were reflective of these psychosocial considerations, further emphasizing the need for focused reconstruction in maintaining both appearance and psychological well-being. By improving vermilion balance, white-roll definition, and nasal projection, the procedure reduced visible deformities that may negatively affect self-image during critical developmental periods.

From a technical perspective, the surgical approach—Mulliken-based scar excision with orbicularis oris repair, dermofat harvest from the gluteal fold, and Tajima's reverse-U incision with lower lateral cartilage repositioning aligns with current recommendations for secondary cleft lip rhinoplasty. Significant improvements show in nasal symmetry and tip projection using combined cartilage repositioning and soft-tissue augmentation in a large series of secondary cleft lip rhinoplasty patients. Furthermore, dermofat also harmoniously integrates with these established techniques to augment both lip and nasal without cartilage harvest morbidity. Recent literature emphasizes the stability and safety of dermofat grafts in craniofacial reconstruction, with good long-term survival, minimal rates of infection or extrusion, and similar results even in scar tissue or operated fields.^{5,12,14,15} In cleft patients alone, dermofat graft can manage volume deficiency and scar camouflage equally well with high satisfaction and minimal complications. The present case also highlights the practicality of dermofat grafting in the Indonesian healthcare context.⁶

The use of a standardized aesthetic rating system such as the Asher McDade scale adds objectivity to outcomes in nasolabial appearance after cleft lip and nasal surgery. The Asher McDade system evaluates four domains: nasal form, nasal symmetry, nasal profile, and vermilion border, on a 5-point ordinal scale, where 1 represents “very good” appearance and 5 “poor”.¹⁶ In our patient, assigning preoperative scores using this scale helped quantify deformities (high scores for vermilion border discontinuity and nasal profile flattening). Postoperatively, improvements in these domains are reflected by lower scores, demonstrating that our technique achieved measurable aesthetic enhancement according to an established evaluation metric.

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The present case also highlights the practicality of dermofat grafting in the Indonesian healthcare context. Access to synthetic implants can be limited, while harvesting costal cartilage adds morbidity and operative complexity. Dermofat, harvested from readily available donor sites such as the gluteal fold, provides a safe, autologous, and cost-effective option. By enabling simultaneous correction of multiple deformities in one stage, dermofat grafting reduces surgical burden, travel costs, and psychological stress for families—factors especially relevant in resource-limited settings. This makes dermofat an attractive reconstructive strategy in Indonesia, where minimizing staged interventions is often critical to improving both functional and psychosocial outcomes.

CONCLUSIONS

This case shows that dermofat grafting is an effective single-stage method for correcting secondary cleft lip and nasal deformities, including vermilion asymmetry, white-roll deficiency, and nasal tip projection. It works well with standard techniques, providing lasting soft-tissue support, muscle function, and improved appearance. The procedure also reduces the stress of multiple surgeries and increases patient satisfaction, especially in children. With low complication rates and easy availability, dermofat grafting is a practical option in Indonesia. Early results are promising, but long-term studies are needed.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

All the authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

ETHICS APPROVAL

Informed consent has been acquired from the guardian (father). The patient's guardian provided written informed consent to be published as a case report.

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